

SURVEILLANCE CARD_ WNF_Pathogen detection in wild birds affected by neurological symptoms or sudden death (caught or dead)

	Characteristics	Description
1	Surveillance component name	Pathogen detection in wild birds affected by neurological symptoms or sudden death (catches and dead) testing for West Nile Virus.
2	Surveillance aim	Early detection of the introduction of the pathogen; early detection of a change of the geographic distribution/spread to new areas.
3	Target species and group	Wild birds: blackbird and the magpie are the target birds to be used in virus surveillance.
4	Target sector / production type	Not applicable.
5	Geographical area covered	All countries with presence of the competent mosquito vector - all European countries, except Iceland and Faroe Islands, and in all Middle Eastern and North African countries. Country-wide.
6	Age group	Animals that have reached an adequate level of immune maturity.
7	Sampling point and strategy	Areas of sudden mortality of wild birds with symptoms including neurological manifestations; areas with the greatest presence of wild bird species. Testing should be applied to all animals found dead, possibly enhanced by caught animals.
8	Sampling time period	Year-round / not limited; minimum annual time frame with the greatest diffusion of vectors: from March to November. (1)
9	Sampling matrix	Birds' tissues including brain, heart or liver. (2)
10	Type of disease indicators	Identification of the agent (virus detection and isolation).
11	Sampling unit	Single or multiple samples based on the number of the identified cases of disease (sudden mortality of wild birds with symptoms including neurological manifestations). [3]
12	Allocation of animal groups /animals to sampling	Targeted based on clinical signs or sudden-death.

13	Testing protocol / Diagnostic test	Serological Tests: Antibody can be identified in serum by IgM capture enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (IgM capture ELISA), haemagglutination inhibition (HI), IgG ELISA, plaque reduction neutralisation (PRN), and microtitre virus neutralisation (VN). The IgM capture ELISA is particularly useful for detecting equine antibodies resulting from recent natural exposure to WNV. The PRN test is the most specific among WNV serological tests; WN vaccination history must be considered in interpretation of serology results, particularly in the PRN and VN tests and IgG ELISA.(4)
14	Design prevalence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	Not applicable; biased (non-random or non-representative) sample of the population.
15	Level of confidence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	Not applicable; biased (non-random or non-representative) sample of the population.
16	Contribution of the component to the surveillance system	Complementary method to the standard epidemiological surveillance on insect vectors and humans.
17	Other pathogens that could be targeted with this surveillance component	Highly Pathogenic Avian Influenza (HPAI).
18	References	<p>1) ECDC Culex pipiens - Factsheet for experts, last updated 15 Jun 2020</p> <p>2) WOAH Terrestrial Manual Chapter 3.1.25. about West Nile fever (version adopted in May 2018)</p> <p>3) Sofia M, Giannakopoulos A, Giantsis IA, Touloudi A, Birtsas P, Papageorgiou K, Athanasakopoulou Z, Chatzopoulos DC, Vrioni G, Galamatis D, Diamantopoulos V, Mpellou S, Petridou E, Kritas SK, Palli M, Georgakopoulos G, Spyrou V, Tsakris A, Chaskopoulou A, Billinis C. West Nile Virus Occurrence and Ecological Niche Modeling in Wild Bird Species and Mosquito Vectors: An Active Surveillance Program in the Peloponnese Region of Greece. <i>Microorganisms</i>. 2022 Jun 30;10(7):1328. doi: 10.3390/microorganisms10071328. PMID: 35889046; PMCID: PMC9320058.</p>

		4) WOHAI about disease – West Nile Fever, last updated 2022 5) IZSVE - West Nile: the monitoring of wild birds for virus surveillance, Research and Projects, 2017
19	Additional comments	Prevalence information available: 78 % (5)